

Journal: **International Journal of Business Management (ISSN 2348-7458)**

Article ID: **IJOBM-17-417 Friday Igbatigbi.**

DOI: **10.15415/ijobm.2019.0828**

Author(s): **Friday Igbatigbi.**

Title: ***THE CHALLENGES OF POLITICAL LEADERSHIP IN NIGERIA.***

Acceptance Letter

Dear Mr. Friday Igbatigbi,

Congratulation, I am pleased to inform you that your article (**DOI: 10.15415/ijobm.2019.0828**) has been accepted for publication in the **INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT.**

There are some corrections (typographical, grammatical etc.) which we will effect before the gallery proof will be sent to you for corrections (if any).

Remember corresponding authors are charged a \$200 handling fee. Payment and transaction process should be directed to

Account Department via email: iajoss@ojournal.site

Indexing Body and Partners: ISI, Open J-Gate, Journal Seek, DOAJ, Union Catalogue, University of California Library, National Library of Sweden, Scholars Portal, University Library, Saskatchewan, The University of Georgia Library, Chemical Abstracts (USA), University of Oregon Library, University of Groningen Library, State Library of New South Wales, Colorado State University Library, Ghent University, Belgium, WZB Library, Germany, Periodicos, Scotland Knowledge Network, Covered by SLUB, CABI, Google Scholar, Research Journal Seeker

Thank you for sending your manuscript to **International Journal of Business Management.**

Regards

Prof. Remy Alexander

Editor,

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

Online International Journals

Please always quote the Article ID in all correspondence.